

Designing a low carbon cropping system: Relay-cropping, a method of producing two crops a year

Problem

The main problem that we aimed to address within our low carbon cropping system was to reduce carbon emissions while increasing the production of biomass. Another objective was to improve the economic benefits of the system by growing a commercial relay crop.

Solution

The low carbon cropping system that we designed consists of 2 overlapping crops with shifted growing cycles (winter crop and spring crop). The first crop is sown in 2 rows out of 3. The second crop is sown in the free row while the first is developing. The harvests are shifted too, with the first harvest being on the usual date and the second in autumn.

Benefits

If the second crop has sufficient time to mature and complete its cycle, the cumulative yield from the field exceeds that of the first crop. Also, one of the crops may be grown as a biofuel, thus substituting the use of fossil fuel during production. Furthermore, the soil is covered for a longer period of time which will also provide ecosystem services due to the increase in biodiversity. The quantities of carbon returned to the soil are greater than with a single crop and will improve fertility in the long term.

Applicability box

Theme

Multiple cropping, rotation, cropping system

Agronomic conditions

Tested in chalky soil in northeast of France on an arable crop farm.

Application time

Every year between a winter cereal and a second crop sown late (spring sowing)

Required time

The extra time required is during the second sowing and the second harvest but this time is quite close to the one needed to manage a service crop (for example a catch-crop).

Period of impact

Late summer and autumn between two main crops

Equipment

In our case, we used a precision seed drill. It is mounted behind a strip till to till the soil. A 22.5 cm offset hitch is necessary for the tractor wheels to pass over the free row

Best in

This technique can be practiced in all types of cropping system

Picture 1: Here sugarbeet is sown at the beginning of April in wheat sown in October. Picture 2: Wheat harvesting in July. Picture 3: Sugarbeet in August.

Practical recommendations

- We combined a winter cereal and sugar beet as spring crops.
- Adapt the spacing of the seed drill for the first crop to the spacing of the seed drill for the second so that it is well centred in the row spacing. In our case, the second crop was sown with a precision seed drill with a 45 cm spacing. We therefore adjusted the first seeder to a spacing of 15 cm to leave a free row every 45 cm
- The sowing of the first crop is constrained by the spacing of the seeder of the second crop. Wider spacing of the seeder rows of the second crop (eg 60-75cm) may allow the first crop to create less shade for the second crop.
- Herbicide application on the first crop (winter cereal) is preferably performed in the autumn to avoid the probable phytotoxicity of spring chemical weeding
- Lower the plant density of the first crop. Our tests show that in order not to suffocate the second crop and obtain a satisfactory yield, the sowing density should be between 50% and 70% of the usual density
- If the cereal has an erect growth habit, the sowing density may be a little higher because such canopy naturally allows more light to pass through
- For a winter cereal we recommend sowing it every third row to promote access to light for the second crop
- Sowing depth of the second crop should be greater than usual to increase access to moisture and avoid predation by rodents or birds
- For the second crop, give preference to low-growing crops to avoid them being mowed by the combine harvester, or use crops that support cutting such as multi-cut sorghum. In this case study we tested corn and sunflower. Only the leaf tips of the corn were cut off during the first harvest, which meant that it could continue to grow and was suitable for relay cropping. However, the sunflower sought the light and overtook the wheat and was cut during the wheat harvest, meaning that it was not successful as a relay crop.
- Use a good direct seed drill or use a precision seed drill mounted behind a strip-till to till the soil
- The development of this technique is still underway at Terrasolis Farm. Its results are satisfactory only if there is sufficient rain for the second crop to grow properly specifically at the beginning of their development.

Further information

Video

- Check the following video for further instructions (French language). <https://bit.ly/3tdHpCu>

Weblinks

- www.terrasolis.fr

About this practice abstract and DiverIMPACTS

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This practice abstract was elaborated in the DiverIMPACTS project, based on the EIP AGRI practice abstract format. It was tested on plots in strips 8m wide with farmers' equipment.

DiverIMPACTS: The project is running from June 2017 to May 2022. The overall goal of DiverIMPACTS - Diversification through Rotation, Intercropping, Multiple Cropping, Promoted with Actors and value-Chains towards Sustainability - is to achieve the full potential of diversification of cropping systems for improved productivity, delivery of ecosystem services and resource-efficient and sustainable value chains.

Project website: www.diverimpacts.net

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